

Digital Democracy Grading Toolkit

Authors

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Abstract

The toolkit is part of INNOVADE's set of tools to evaluate how well digital democracy tools and projects work in promoting democratic participation. It includes a survey that helps assess the level of a particular digital democracy technology or project. Based on the survey results, the toolkit generates a score that reflects the project's level of digital democracy. The score highlights areas where steps could be taken to improve civic participation in democratic processes through digital means.

Benefits

- To measure the democratic quality of digital participation tools using standardized, research-based metrics.
- To identify specific gaps in inclusivity, transparency, and accountability within existing digital governance platforms.
- To provide recommendations to enhance the democratic depth and impact of digital initiatives.
- To align digital tools with evidence-based standards for resilient and effective public engagement.

Why is it important?

The Digital Democracy Scoring is vital for moving beyond "token" participation. By providing clear benchmarks, it helps organizations ensure their digital tools are transparent and inclusive, turning online engagement into a trusted and impactful democratic process.

Online resource

The Digital Democracy Grading Toolkit is available for free online:
<https://www.digital-democracy.net>

Involved

Stakeholders

Policymakers &
policy-facing CSOs,
Public Administration

Citizens &
citizen-
facing CSOs

Quote

"There is not one single digital democracy. There are different forms and models of digital democracy. The Digital Democracy Score takes this diversity into account. It is highly flexible and well suited to measuring different varieties of digital democracy. The tool calculates up to six distinct scores and combines them into one overall score: the Digital Democracy Score."

Prof. Christian Fuchs, leader of the Paderborn University-research team